

Study of Prevalence of Childhood Seizures and EEG Changes in Specific Language Impairment Children in Bihar

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Abstract:

When there is no clear explanation for a language impairment, such as autism, mental retardation, cleft lip or palate, severe neurological or neuromuscular disorders affecting the speech apparatus, or impaired hearing, the condition is referred to as specific language impairment (SLI). The objective of the study was to evaluate the frequency of juvenile seizures and EEG alterations in particular linguistic impairment. Of the 100 SLI patients, 16 (80% of the patients) were male and 4 (20%) were female, with a history indicative of seizures in 20% of the patients. Of the twenty, twelve (n = 60%) had generalised tonic-clonic seizures, five (n = 25%) had myoclonic seizures, and three (n = 15%) had a documented history of status epilepticus. The EEG results revealed that 5(25%) had generalised epileptiform changes, 3(15%) had focal epileptiform changes, 3(15%) had myoeptileptiform changes, 2(10%) had both generalised and myoeptileptiform changes, and 2(10%) had nonepileptiform alterations. 5(25%) had normal EEG readings. The recent study found that among this cohort of kids with specific language disability, there was a strong correlation between seizures. Seizures by themselves are not likely to be the cause of SLI problems because of its complex aetiology. Aside from other risk factors, prenatal and perinatal insults could be the cause of SLI development. Seizures should be screened for in order to screen such children for the development of specific language impairment, especially if they occur during infancy.

Keywords: Specific Language Impairment, Seizures, EEG.

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Introduction

A fundamental basis of human intelligence is language which constitutes an important part of human culture. Any insult to the language areas of the developing brain may result in impairment, depending upon the area of the brain bearing the brunt of the pathology.

Based on a threshold of fewer than 50 words, the incidence of expressive language impairments at 24 months of age ranges from 10% to 20%. Boys exhibit higher rates of delay compared to girls [1]. These problems are significant as they impede the child's capacity to communicate and acquire knowledge [2].

Common causes of language disorders include impaired hearing, mental retardation, cleft lip/palate, gross neurological or neuromuscular abnormalities affecting the speech apparatus, and autism. One large group comprises of children in whom speech and language abnormality is not a result of any of these aforementioned causes and this group of children is designated as having specific language impairment (SLI).

Plausible risk factors for specific developmental language disorders are male gender, low birth weight, prematurity, neurometabolic disorders, structural abnormalities of brain, neurogenetic disorders, history of seizures, family history of seizures, etc. However, not all the children who develop perinatal problems, develop specific developmental language disorders. Seizures, particularly during infancy, constitute the commonest clinical manifestations of neurological dysfunction in an infant [3-5], it is therefore reasonable to assume that seizures may later affect the speech & language development.

The study aimed to assess the prevalence of childhood seizures and EEG changes in specific language impairment children.

Materials and Method

The present study was conducted in the Department of Physiology, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna in association with Pediatric OPD in Department of Pediatrics. The study assessed children aged 2-8 years who mostly exhibited speech and

language impairment for potential involvement. Those having global motor developmental delay, head injury, gross hearing impairment, structural abnormalities of lips, tongue palate such as cleft lip/palate and autism were excluded from the study. These criteria corresponded closely with the definition of SLI.

Finally, 100 patients were selected having specific developmental language disorder, of which 24 were girls and 76 boys. Upon receiving approval from the institutional ethical committee, the study received informed consent from the parents of the children. The goal of the study was thoroughly explained to the parents. The parents were then interviewed to get a comprehensive medical history of the patients, which encompassed information about the period before birth, during birth, and after birth. Specifically, the history included details about any speech and language impairments, seizures, and neurodevelopmental issues in the family. 20% of the children, or 20 out of 100, reported a history of seizures. Subsequently, these youngsters underwent a comprehensive neurological assessment conducted by a specialist in paediatric neurology.

Standard video EEG was conducted on all of these individuals for a minimum duration of 40 minutes in order to record both wakefulness and stage II non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep. Bipolar and referential montages were employed in accordance with the 10:20 worldwide method of recording. A skilled paediatric neurologist and electrophysiologist carefully examined the EEG records to detect any epileptiform or other alterations.

The International Federation of Societies for Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology (IFSECN) has defined epileptiform waves or activity as distinctive waves or complexes that can be distinguished from background activity and resemble those recorded in

some individuals with epileptic disorders [6].

Results and Discussion

Epidemiological Characteristics

The ultimate group consisted of 100 children aged 2 to 8 years, with 76 (76%) being males and 24 (24%) being females, resulting in a sex ratio of 3.2:1. This closely aligns with the research conducted by Shriberg, Tomblin, and McSweeny in 1999 (4). Being male is considered a significant risk factor for language-related changes due to the slower maturation of the nervous system in boys. This slower maturation makes boys more vulnerable to changes in general. Additionally, the influence of testosterone inhibits cell death and makes it difficult to establish proper connections, which can have a negative effect on the development of language skills in male individuals [5].

The average age of the entire cohort was 50.3 ± 19.7 months, with female children having an average age of 49.3 ± 19.5 months and male children having an average age of 51.3 ± 20.0 months.

Seizures

About one fifth 20 (20%) out of 100 children had history suggestive of seizures, of which 16 (80%) were males and 4 (20%) females. (Table 1)

Thus an unexpectedly high frequency of previous history of seizures is observed in the present cohort as compared to normal population where the prevalence ranges from 3.2-5.5/1,000 in developed countries and 3.6-44/1,000 in underdeveloped countries [7].

Six (30%) developed seizures during their neonatal period; 10 (50%) had their first seizure during their second month to 12th month of life, and rest 4 (20%) in their second year of life.

Table 1: Predisposing characteristics for SLI in seizure patients

Age of onset of seizures	Neonatal (< 1 month)	6
	Infantile (1-12 months)	10
	Childhood (>1 year)	4
Types of seizures	Generalized Tonic-Clonic	12
	Myoclonic	5
	Status Epilepticus	3
EEG changes	Normal EEG	5
	Generalized epileptiform	5
	Focal epileptiform	3
	Multifocal epileptiform	3
	Generalized & Multifocal epileptiform	2
	Non- epileptiform	2
Other associated conditions	Positive family history	5
	Gender (M:F)	3.2:1
	Asphyxia at birth	3

	LSCS (delayed labor, maternal diabetes)	2
	Hyperactivity	9
	Delayed milestones	11

Table 2: Gender wise distribution of patients according to status of history of seizures

Sex	History of seizures		Total
	Yes	No	
Male	16	60	76
Female	4	20	24
Total	20	80	100

Figure 1: Prevalence of seizures in SLI

Seizures during infancy may be a sign of a mild neurodevelopmental risk that could later show up as particular learning challenges or a lack of social skills [8]. The majority of patients (60%) who experienced seizures had generalised tonic-clonic seizures (n = 12). Myoclonic seizures were seen in 25% of the patients (n = 5). An additional 15% (n=3) had a history of status epilepticus, which finally resulted in encephalopathy. There is proof that one youngster who had myoclonic seizures had hypocalcaemia.

EEG Changes

15 out of 20 (75%) patients with seizures showed an abnormal EEG as compared to 30 out of 80 (37.5%) patients without seizures. This difference was also found statistically considerable (p=0.01). In patients with abnormal EEG, higher proportion (33.3%) of the patients had history of seizures compared to patients with normal EEG (9.1%). This difference was also found statistically considerable (p=0.01, Table 3)

Table 3: Distribution of patients showing abnormal EEG with history of Seizures

Status of EEG	History of seizures		Total
	Yes	No	
Normal	5	50	55
Abnormal	15	30	45
Total	20	80	100
P value	0.01		

Five patients with seizures showed a normal EEG; 13 showed abnormalities labeled as epileptic: interictal discharges, focal spikes or paroxysmal bursts of spike/ wave activity. Another 2 showed abnormalities, which were not specifically epileptic

such as intermittent sharp waves from P3 and sudden appearance of theta activity in one and slow for age & paucity of normal features of stage II NREM sleep in another patient.

Figure 2: Prevalence of EEG in SLI

The present study is also in agreement with a study by Aina et al which showed a positive connection among SLI, seizures, hyperactivity etc [13].

Seizures are a severe issue that children with developmental speech difficulties frequently experience, according to previous research [14].

Additionally, some research has shown that aberrant electroencephalogram recordings might be seen even in the absence of clinical seizures [15].

Conclusion

In this cohort of children with specific language impairment, the current investigation found a strong correlation between seizures and generalised epileptiform changes (GEG changes), with GTCS being the most common type of seizure. Such a correlation has also been reported in other investigations [17, 18]. Language impairments may result from seizures through direct damage to language centres or through aberrant development of the brain. Since the aetiology of SLI is well recognised to be complex, seizures by themselves cannot be the cause of these problems. These illnesses arise as a result of prenatal and natal insults as well as other risk factors. Seizures should be screened for in order to screen such children for the development of specific language impairment, especially if they occur during infancy.

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